

Imposter Syndrome Among Medical Students of Private Medical College, Lahore, Pakistan

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ABSTRACT

Objective: The aim of this study is to determine the total prevalence, year of study-wise as well as the gender-wise distribution of Impostor Syndrome (IS) amongst the undergraduate medical students at CMH Lahore Medical College, using the eight-question questionnaire of the Young Impostor Scale (YIS).

Study design: The study was cross sectional and descriptive survey.

Place and duration of study: Conducted in CMH Lahore Medical College from January to April 2018.

Methods: A total of 260 students from five years of MBBS and from both genders were enrolled in the study. Non-probability convenient sampling technique was used. The Youngs Impostor Scale (YIS) was used as the questionnaire.

Results: A total of 79(30.4%) students were positive whilst 181(69.6%) were negative for impostor syndrome.

Class-wise distribution shows Impostor syndrome to be most prevalent in students of 2nd year (9.2%) out of the 5 MBBS classes.

Also, impostor syndrome is more prevalent in the female (38.8%) population than male (25.35%) and this difference is statistically significant ($p=0.02$).

Keywords: Prevalence, Impostor syndrome, medical students.

INTRODUCTION

Coined for the first time by Dr. Pauline Clance, the impostor phenomenon was described as an individual's experience of feeling inept and of having misled others about his or her own capabilities.¹ These individuals are usually exceedingly successful but are unable to associate their achievements with their personal abilities and rather attribute them with luck.² Clance pointed out that the fear of failure is their main driving force and they therefore, overextend themselves in any task assigned to them in order to reduce the risk of failure. This phenomenon greatly hinders the individual's personal well being while promoting feelings of self-doubt and apprehension. To remove these negative feelings, "Impostors" overwork themselves to prove that they are adept and capable. They feel extremely anxious when they are exposed to a demanding task as they live in constant fear of being exposed of their "phoniness".³ They therefore also tend to be exceedingly critical of their efforts and accomplishments, finding it difficult to accept any form of praise for their achievements. Remaining fixated on their flaws as they are afraid of mortification, they will constantly focus on negative feedback as a reason for any mistake they might make. Lastly, these individuals also tend to overvalue others' intelligence and proficiency by comparing others' strengths with their own weaknesses.²

The initial observations on the impostor phenomenon

were clinical, being recorded from therapeutic sessions with highly accomplished females only as this group was considered susceptible due to their role in society and their family dynamics.^{1,3} Following researches however were conducted on non-clinical populations such as undergraduate students and found that the impostor phenomenon is equally prevalent amongst males as well, with some authors even reporting a greater prevalence in them than in females.^{2,3} Subsequent studies also went on to establish a positive correlation between impostor syndrome and certain personality traits of an individual. In a study conducted by Chae et al. he found neuroticism and perfectionism amongst individuals to be strongly related with the development of the impostor phenomenon.³

In a world with increasing levels of competitiveness amongst peers, medical students, by virtue of the medical profession, are increasingly susceptible to emotional strain and anxiety. They have to meet with increased expectations of the education system precipitating stress and psychiatric morbidity such as depression and GAD (General Anxiety Disorders) in them. These circumstances set off a phenomenon amongst them known as 'Burnout'. Burnout is defined as a state of prolonged stress leading to physical and emotional exhaustion, cynicism, detachment, feelings of inadequacy, and a lack of accomplishment. Due to the taxing nature of medical education, burnout seems to be experienced by virtually every medical student today and is becoming an increasingly known phenomenon over time.⁴ A striking resemblance can be noted amongst the characteristics experienced by an individual

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experiencing burnout and imposter syndrome (e.g. feeling of inadequacy). The syndrome has gained significant popularity during the last few years due to its association with burnout and its relevance today to people in several different fields and belonging to various cultures around the world.^{3,5}

This phenomenon is especially important for medical students today as the growth in Knowledge over time has severely added to the stressors they have to face. According to a study conducted by Henning et al., higher levels of psychological distress were reported amongst undergraduate medical students as compared to the general population. The importance of the imposter phenomenon to medical students can further be reflected by the fact that the imposter syndrome was considered to be an important indicator for the development of psychological stress amongst the students in this study. In another study conducted by Qureshi et al. on final year medical students in a Medical University in Lahore, Pakistan, 47.5%(68) of the total 143 students reported with Impostor Syndrome according to the Young Impostor Scale (YIS). Out of the sixty-eight, 53.5%(45) of them were female while only 38.9%(23) were males.^{5,6} These findings also reflect the need to further investigate the prevalence of imposter syndrome amongst Pakistani medical students at other institutes in order to better understand the problem. A more thorough research into the matter can help in identifying the causes and in developing possible solutions to the problems faced by several medical students today.

This aim of this study is to determine the total prevalence, year of study-wise as well as the gender-wise distribution of Impostor Syndrome amongst the undergraduate medical students at CMH Lahore Medical College, using the eight-question questionnaire of the Young Impostor Scale (YIS).

METHODS

The study was a cross sectional one, conducted at CMH Lahore Medical College, a private medical college in Lahore, Pakistan from January to April 2018. A sample size calculation software by RAOSOFT Inc, was used to calculate the sample size of a total of 260 students (confidence interval: 95%, margin of error: 5% and response distribution: 47.5%). Samples were collected from all five years of MBBS students and both genders were enrolled in the study. A convenient, non-probability type sampling technique was used to include 52 students each from every year of study (first to fifth) of giving a total sample of 260. Only students enrolled in the five years of MBBS were included and students studying dentistry (BDS) were excluded.

A verbal informed consent was taken after which the students were introduced to and asked to fill the printed questionnaires anonymously.

The Youngs Imposter Scale (YIS) was used as the questionnaire. The reliability of YIS was done with the help of the software, SPSS version 23 (IBM Corporation, Armonk, NY, USA). Eight questions were used to do the dichotomous assessment of imposter syndrome; Present (Yes) or Absent (No). If a student answered five or more questions as "Yes", he/she was considered positive for Imposter Syndrome. SPSS version 23 software (IBM Corporation, Armonk, NY, USA) was used for the Statistical analysis. The year wise and gender wise distribution (percentage) of Imposter syndrome was calculated for the total sample. A gender wise distribution was calculated for the responses. A bar chart was used to represent the gender wise distribution of the total sample.

RESULTS

Out of 300 students 260(86.7%) completed the questionnaire. Out of which 162(62.3%) were males and 98(37.7%) were females.

Students responding "Yes" to 5 or more on the Young Imposters scale were categorized as positive. A total of 79(30.4%) students were positive whilst 181(69.6%) were negative for IS.

Class-wise distribution given in table 1, shows Imposter syndrome to be most prevalent in students of 2nd year (9.2% out of the 5 MBBS classes)(p=0.01)

DISCUSSION

An individual suffering from imposter syndrome will not be confident in himself and will consider his achievements to be due to luck and such individuals criticize themselves severely. A link has also been discovered between imposter syndrome and a low educational self-esteem.⁷ Low self esteem is evident in a significant portion of the male subjects who reported 'yes'(62.2%) to "When you do succeed, do you think, "Phew" I fooled them this time but I may not be that lucky next time?".

Our study reports a higher incidence of Imposters syndrome in females (38.8% of all females) consistent with the findings reported by Qureshi et al, Ghorbanshirodi et al and Villwock et al. (5,7,8). It has also been proven by other studies that women have lower self-esteem than their male counterparts.⁹

A study done on Austrian doctoral students has shown a decrease in self-efficacy of women. This has led to the development of Imposter Syndrome amongst the female doctoral students, suggesting that Imposters syndrome is a psychological barrier in women's university careers.

According to the Pakistan Medical and Dental Council (PMDC), the number of female Doctors is almost equal to that of male doctors¹⁰ which shows that the effects of this syndrome could be far reaching. Women are commonly perceived as less successful and less goal

Table 1: Imposters Syndrome frequency distribution according to year of study

Class	Imposters syndrome positive	Imposters syndrome Absent	Total
1 st year	8(15.7%)	41(84.3%)	51
2 nd year	24(44.4%)	30(55.6%)	54
3 rd year	17(32.7%)	35(67.3%)	52
4 th year	18(34.6%)	34(65.4%)	52
5 th year	12(23.5%)	39(76.5%)	51

*Pearson's chi square test is significant p=0.01
Gender-wise details of responses are given in Table 2.

Table 2: Gender-wise distribution of responses.

No	Questions	Answer (Yes/No)	Males(%)	Female(%)
1	Do you secretly worry that others will find out that you are not as bright and capable as they think you are?	Yes	53(54.6%)	44(45.4%)
		No	109(66.9%)	54(33.1%)
2	Do you sometimes shy away from challenges because of a nagging self doubt	Yes	68(57.1%)	51(42.9%)
		No	94(66.7%)	47(33.3%)
3	Do you tend to chalk your accomplishments up to being a fluke no big deal or the fact that people just like you?	Yes	62(57.9%)	45(42.1%)
		No	100(65.4%)	53(34.6%)
4	Do you hate making a mistake, being less than fully prepared or not doing things perfectly?	Yes	98(60.9%)	44(45.4%)
		No	64(64.6%)	63(39.4%)
5	Do you tend to feel crushed even by constructive criticism, seeing it as an evidence of your ineptness?	Yes	47(52.2%)	43(47.8%)
		No	115(67.6%)	55(32.4%)
6	When you do succeed, do you think, “Phew” I fooled them this time but I may not be that lucky next time?	Yes	56(62.2%)	34(37.6%)
		No	106(62.3%)	98(37.7%)
7	Do you believe that other people (students,colleagues, competitors) are smarter and more capable than you?	Yes	47(52.2%)	43(47.8%)
		No	81(53.6%)	70(46.4%)
8	Do you live in fear of being found out, discovered or un-masked?	Yes	43(58.9%)	30(41.1%)
		No	119(63.6%)	68(36.4%)

According to Table 3, which gives frequency of Imposters syndrome amongst the genders, imposter syndrome is more prevalent in the female (38.8%) population than male (25.35%) (p=0.02).

Table 3: Gender * Imposter Syndrome Cross tabulation

			Imposter Syndrome		Total
			present	absent	
Gender	Male	Count	41	121	162
		% within Gender	25.3%	74.7%	100.0%
Female		Count	38	60	98
		% within Gender	38.8%	61.2%	100.0%
Total		Count	79	181	260
		% within Gender	30.4%	69.6%	100.0%

*Pearsons chi square test is significant <0.05

oriented than their male counterparts¹¹ and this could explain the higher prevalence of imposter syndrome in the female population as Imposters syndrome has also been inversely linked to a persons self-esteem.⁷ Introjections of societal sex-role stereotyping also appear to contribute significantly to the development of the impostor phenomenon. Despite outstanding academic and professional accomplishments, women who experience the imposter phenomenon persist in believing that they are really not bright and have fooled anyone who thinks so.¹

Imposter syndrome has also been linked to social anxiety, self deprecation and depression all of which can further cause less females to further themselves in their career path.

Females reported 'yes' most frequently (47.8%) to "Do you tend to feel crushed even by constructive criticism, seeing it as an evidence of your ineptness?" indicating that they perceive any form of criticism as a sign of failure, which can hamper their professional growth severely. This finding is also consistent with another study which states that the Imposter syndrome may cause students to be socially withdrawn in order to hide their assumed fraudulence as they consider their success to be due to external factors rather than it being due to their natural abilities. They resist and avoid any sort of encouragement or praise and may eventually seclude themselves entirely from the outside world (Cardenas, 2016).

A link has also been established between Imposters syndrome and the parental over protection score¹², of which females in an eastern society are more prone to be subject to.

Males have reported a lower prevalence of imposter syndrome (25.3% out of all males). It is also reported that male students suffer less burnout than their female counterparts and have lesser perceived impact of stressors, leading to decreased rates of exhaustion.⁴

In conclusion, our study reports the highest rate of imposter syndrome amongst students of 2nd year of MBBS, which differs from the findings reported by Villwock et al.⁸ Students of 2nd year MBBS have a solely theoretical based curriculum with limited clinical exposure, which might make them feel anxious about the responsibilities they will have to shoulder in the coming years.⁷ Thus programs to help students and teachers identify this and help students overcome this issue should be initiated in all years of study.

Imposter syndrome is diagnosed most frequently after psychotherapies as a sufferer normally tries to hide this aspect. Group therapies are seen as highly effective.¹ Hence advocacy and awareness are imperative for its treatment. The ideal mode of treatment for these individuals, however, is cognitive therapy as well as

gestalt therapy.

The limitations of this study include the use of a convenient nonprobability sampling technique in only one private medical college and a small sample size. It would be more significant if the study is done at multiple centers with a significantly large number of students. For future research, we recommend the use of a longitudinal survey using a cohort throughout the training process of the students as this could elucidate whether "once an impostor, always an impostor" or whether impostor tendencies tend to resolve spontaneously with time and experience. No demographic data was collected for non respondents, preventing us from assessing the degree to which selection bias may have occurred.

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